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Experimental evaluation of the isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Zr ternary system at 1273 KZhara Kahrobaee, Frank Stein and Martin Palm

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Introduction

Ti–Al alloys comprise a new class of intermetallic materials, targeted for more energy-efficient automotive and aircraft engines [1]. Their properties at high temperatures, specifically creep and oxidation resistance, can be substantially improved by alloying [2]. Development of new alloys today not any longer solely relies on experimental trials. CALPHAD (CALculation of PHase Diagram) modelling [3], by which phase diagrams and phase transitions can be calculated and from which, e.g., phase fractions in dependence on temperature can be derived, has become an important tool for developing new alloys. The modelling gives essential information about the expected microstructures from which potential properties of novel alloys can be concluded. CALPHAD calculations crucially depend on the underlying database. Within a large-scale collaborative project, the partners Helmholtz-Zentrum Geesthacht, Germany, Montanuniversität Leoben, Austria, Thermo-Calc Software AB, Sweden, and MPIE will essentially improve thermodynamic data for a number of Ti–Al–X(–Y) systems for a next generation of advanced CALPHAD databases for TiAl alloys [4].

Ti–Al–Zr at 1273 K

Phase equilibria in Ti–Al(–X...) systems are highly sensitive to the amount of impurities [5]. Small amounts of oxygen can already lead to significant changes in phase equilibria [6]. As Ti and Zr are extremely prone to oxygen uptake, this could be one reason for existing discrepancies in phase equilibria in the Ti–Al–Zr system, e.g. at 1273 K.

The Ti–Al–Zr system has been critically evaluated by Tretyachenko [7], including three partial isothermal sections. The one at 1273 K merely shows phase equilibria among the phases γ TiAl and α_2 Ti₃Al and those between α Ti, β Ti and α_2 Ti₃Al as dashed lines. The most comprehensive study of phase equilibria at 1273 K was performed by Yang et al. [8]. However, phase equilibria determined in the ternary system do not match well with those established for the Ti–Al subsystem [6]. Figure 1 shows the Ti–Al rich part of the isothermal section as determined in [8] and experimental results from other investigations [9–12]. In addition, the phase boundaries from the latest assessment of the Ti–Al system are given [6]. Figure 1 shows that substantial differences between these investigations exist. E.g., values for the solid solubility of Zr in γ TiAl at 1273 K vary between about 8 at.% [8], 10 at.% [9] or even at least 15 at.% [11].

Materials and Methods

In order to settle these uncertainties, six alloys have been prepared by crucible free levitation melting from high-purity elements. Slices of the manufactured alloys were cut on a diamond wire saw, encapsulated in quartz tubes back-filled with Ar and annealed at 1273 K for 100 h. Ti filings were used as getter to minimize the uptake of impurities. Compositions of the alloys and their impurity contents in the as-cast condition and after heat treatment were established by wet chemical analysis. Phases were identified by X-ray diffraction (XRD) and compositions of the coexisting phases were established by electron probe microanalysis (EPMA).

Fig. 1: Partial isothermal section of the Al-Ti-Zr ternary system at 1273 K. Phase boundaries are from Ref. [8] with additional data from Refs. [6, 9-12].

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